

Project information

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Author(s)	Regina Guenster, Omran Alhaddad
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1. Introduction

The eRImote information platform is the central data base of all information gathered within eRImote and has two components - an internal and public part.

Description	Name to be used in the Project
Internal data platform – access for eRImote consortium only	Internal Data Storage
External data platform – publicly accessible	eRImote Information Platform

Both data storages use the same information structure and document tags for consistency but are available for different audiences. The work described in this deliverable was performed as part of tasks T2.1 and T2.2.

2. Information structure and tag definitions

Initially, the type of information that will be collated and made public during the eRImote project was identified in collaboration with partners involved in WP1 and WP3. This will largely consist of documents (eg policy documents, best practice examples, publications), recordings of webinars, workshops and trainings, and links to external resources. All data will be curated in the project Internal Data Storage and then made publicly accessible online via a custom-made Information Platform. To ensure that information is easily retrievable the data resources need to be categorised and tagged with common keywords and themes related to remote and digital access to improve findability of resources.

The following categories and tags were agreed on for use:

Domain (ESFRI, <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/landscape-analysis/section-1/>)

- **Data, Computing and Digital RI** - Digital Infrastructure (DI) is broadly defined as a set of information and communication technology components that are the foundation of ICT-services. These include typically physical components - computer and networking hardware and facilities - but also various software and network components. RIs: eBrains, SLICES, PRACE...
- **Physical Sciences & Engineering** – EST, ELI ERIC, ESRF, European Spallation Source ERIC...
- **Energy** – RIs: EU-SOLARIS, ECCSEL ERIC...
- **Environment** – RIs: DANUBIUS-RI, ACTRIS, EMSO, EPOS, Euro-ARGO, ICOS, LifeWatch ERIC...
- **Health & Food** – RIs: EMPHASIS, IBISBA, AnaEE, BMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN, ELIXIR, EMBRC, ERINHA, EU-OPENSOURCE, Euro-Biolmaging, Instruct-ERIC, MIRRI...
- **Social & Cultural Innovation** – CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH, ESS ERIC, SHARE ERIC...
- **Generic** – applicable to all domains
- **Other**

Infrastructure type

- **Physical – Distributed** – Multi-sites physical infrastructure e.g. life science ERIC with multiple facilities where users are served
- **Physical – Single sited** – Single sited physical infrastructure e.g. CERN
- **Digital – Distributed** - Multi-sited infrastructure that mainly offer services to its users with digital access, e.g. digital research tools or virtual access (EGI, CESSDA archives...)
- **Digital – Single sited** - Single-sited infrastructures that only offer services to its users in digital format (e.g. e-infrastructures)

- **Digital – not site specific**
- **Generic** – applicable to all infrastructure types
- **Other**

Access type

- **In-person – Infrastructure access** – In-person access to machinery e.g. a microscope
- **In-person - Data access** – In-person access to sensitive data via a site-specific entry point
- **Remote – control of machinery** – e.g. remote control of a microscope, beam line
- **Remote - Job submission** – Job is submitted to a RI for competition by facility staff e.g. mail in sample analysed by facility staff by microscope or data submission for analysis by RI staff.
- **Remote – Sample provision** – Sample (e.g. mouse, cell line...) is sent to the user upon request
- **Remote – Data access** – access to data deposited on a server/drive
- **Hybrid** - any combination of the above
- **Other**

Resource type

- **Practical Guidelines**- Protocols, guides, manuals
- **Requirements Guidelines** - Overarching standards, requirements
- **Policies** – policies, green papers etc
- **Best Practice Examples**
- **Interview**
- **Presentation** – e.g. presentation form the WP3 workshops
- **Scientific papers** – this tag should be used in combination with others, e.g. practical guideline, as applicable
- **Other**

3. Implementation

3.1 Implementation of the Internal Data Storage

The Internal Data Storage was implemented in SharePoint as this software is already in use for collaboration and collation of all other eRImote documents (WP1). The main documents storage site (Figure 1, *Documents* in the toolbar on the left) and the Internal Data Storage (Figure 1, *Resources* in the toolbar on the left) are easily available in the same place for all eRImote consortium members.

Name	Short descrip...	Domain	RI type	Access Type	Resource Type	Language	Reviewed by c...	Published?
A. Rothkirch - Data management at PETRA III_data acquisition, st...	This document describes how data is managed (acquisition, storage and access) at PETRA III	Data, Computing an Physical Sciences	Physical - Single an	Remote - Data acce Remote - Control of	Presentation	English	Yes	✓
D. Wiltshire - Approaches to providing remote access to confiden...	This document describes how remote access to confidential data is provided within the Leibniz Institute for the social sciences	Social and Cultural Data, Computing an	Digital - Distributed	Remote - Data acce	Presentation	English	Yes	✓

Figure 1: Screenshot of the Internal Data Storage in SharePoint.

Collated document and video links ready for publications are deposited and assigned the appropriate meta data by consortium members in the Internal Data Storage. *Name*, *short description* and *language* are text boxes, while *Domain*, *Infrastructure Type*, *Access Type* and *Resource Type* are dropdown menus with the agreed tags.

The data will then be reviewed and approved for publications by the eRImote Coordinator, and subsequently published on the Information platform. To ensure quick turnaround, the Coordinator and project managers authorised to publish data are automatically notified by SharePoint once new documents or videos are available (Coordinator) or approved for publication (project managers).

3.2. Implementation on the public Information Platform

The public information Platform was implemented in SiteBuilder powered by the ARIA software, developed by Instruct-ERIC, which was previously used for the toolkit in the RI-VIS project. To support the features requires for the eRImote Information Platform, document tagging and filtering was developed by the ARIA team and updates to the document block implemented.

Document upload is available on the ARIA backend for authorised project managers to ensure that only approved information is published (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Document upload and metadata assignment in ARIA.

The documents are then made available on the eRImote website via upgraded *document blocks*. Each block can contain one or multiple documents and displays a title, short descriptive text and the relevant document(s) (Figure 3). This allows clustering of thematically related documents or presentations from one training to be displayed together.

Figure 3: Document blocks in SiteBuilder as displayed on the eRImote website.

Additionally, to the block information each document can be assigned a title, short description and tags to give additional information e.g. on the document author (Figure 4). This information is available by clicking the *Details* ion under the document as well as a *Download* option (Figure 3).

Figure 4: Detailed document information displayed on the eRImote website.

The resources are easily accessible on the eRImote website via links in the header (Figure 5) and organised in pages for documents and videos, respectively. In the future additional resource pages for links to external resources etc might be added as needed.

Figure 5: Resources availability on the eRImote website.

Users can filter the available documents through a newly developed *filter block* (Figure 6) for easy access and document retrievability.

Figure 6: Document block on the eRImote website allowing filtering by tags.

3. Outlook

Going forward, the information platform will be maintained by regular content updates and may be extended for new functionality as feedback from tasks (Task 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, Task 4.1, Task 4.2. Task 4.3) and external stakeholders is received.